

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH.

Xasanov Valijon Normurodovich

Termez State University

3rd year student of philology, English language teaching

Abstract: Students' motivation is very important in language learning. It is important to encourage EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students to participate in the learning process. According to Dornyei (1998), motivation is responsible for determining human activity by energizing and directing it. Motivating students can give them a way to achieve their goals. One of the main aspects of a person is communication. According to Lewis (Lewis, Simons, & Fennig, 2014), English is the third most spoken language in the world. Therefore, English is very important to communicate with people around the world. According to Gardner (1985), which has been recognized for a long time, it is recognized that one of the main elements influencing the learning of English language is the learner's motivation.

Keywords: Motivation, EFL (English as a Foreign Language), communication, long-term goals, native speaker, language acquisition, instrumental and integrative motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, motivation, identification and integration.

Everyone can adjust themselves to learn a language. If you want to speak English fluently, read books in the original, learn to understand the spoken language of native speakers of this language correctly and easily, you will have to put in a lot of effort and you will have to spend a lot of time. However, if you have a strong motivation to learn English, the results will not be long in coming. In order not to lose enthusiasm, you need to motivate yourself on the path of knowledge with any available means. There are the following types of motivation: positive; negative; antimotivation. To increase interest in learning English, you need to use different emotions. Positive motivation refers to the corresponding feelings - imagine how confidently you talk with foreigners, successfully negotiate, etc. By drawing this picture in your head, you can visualize your goal and understand how important it is not to delay learning. Negative motivation for learning English includes negative emotions and

causes anxiety. Just imagine how ridiculous you'll look when you're in a foreign country and don't speak English well enough. Although concern about your future happiness can be a strong reason to work harder and harder, ideally it is desirable to combine positive and negative motivation. The only thing to avoid is antimotivation -

the burden of emotions associated with learning English. If you have experienced failures, ridicule, conflicts in the past, as a result of which you constantly hate the language, you need to overcome this situation and convince yourself that you really need English.

Foreign psychologists, including Western researchers, emphasize that internal and external motivation play a key role in the effectiveness of the educational process. Based on the "self-learning (or self-determination) theory", we can say that two sources can motivate students to study and get education. These are internal and external factors. In general, there are two types of motivation in this place: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. A stimulus directed at a person in this place is an internal stimulus. This motivating factor can be biological, emotional, spiritual or social in nature. In this case, there is no external incentive or reward. This activity is done for self-pleasure and individual satisfaction. This condition can be characterized by curiosity and a desire to overcome difficulties. Intrinsic motivation that a person feels and feels in the process of reading is driven by interest or pleasure. It is more related to inner individuality, that is, it does not rely on external influences. Researchers like Ryan and Desi tried to explain intrinsic motivation without taking into account the external component. According to them, students are engaged in (educational) activities due to their internal interests, joy and excitement, and for this reason, they also have internal motivation. According to Matt and Dale, intrinsic motivators include an interest in a subject, a sense of its connection to life and the world, a sense of accomplishment in mastering it, and a sense of calling to it. Harter explains that intrinsic motivation is a real drive in human nature that drives people to explore and solve new problems.

Desi said, "Intrinsic motivation refers to the pleasure and satisfaction derived from participation in an activity for its own sake." Intrinsic motivation is the internal force that motivates students to engage in learning activities because they are interested in learning and enjoy the learning process. Their (students') abilities are tested (or tested) and they are motivated and interested in learning even if there are no external rewards to be won. Students who have the goals of trying to understand the subject matter and master the skills are said to be intrinsically motivated. Students' needs can motivate them to achieve learning goals.

References:

1. Al-Bustan, S. A., & Al-Bustan, L. (2009). Investigating students attitudes and preferences towards learning English at Kuwait university. *College student journal*, 43(2), 454-464.
2. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. NY: Plenum Publishing Co
3. Dörnyei, Z. (1998). Motivation in second and foreign language learning. *Language teaching*, 31(3), 117-135
4. Gardner, M. P. (1985). Mood states and consumer behavior: A critical review. *Journal of Consumer research*, 12(3), 281-300.
5. Gardner, R. C., Lalonde, R. N., & Moorcroft, R. (1985). The role of attitudes and motivation in second language learning: Correlational and experimental considerations. *Language learning*, 35(2), 207-227.
6. Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second language learning*.
7. Harmer, J. (2007). *The practice of English language teaching* 4th ed. England: Pearson Education Limited